

APPLICATION OF A TITANIUM – CARBON FIBRE METAL LAMINATE IN AN IN-FLIGHT OPENING FIGHTER DOOR LOADED IN ACOUSTIC FATIGUE

Part 2: Production

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the production aspects of an in-flight opening fighter door consisting of titanium-carbon fibre metal laminate (FML) skins and a composite inner structure. A parameter study into the most weight efficient material combination for the FML skins, together with an availability study, resulted in a Titanium 6-4 alloy with a Cyanate ester IM7 composite. All titanium layers were treated with a solgel surface treatment prior to primer application. The flat outer skin was produced in a conventional prepreg lay-up autoclave cycle. For the double curved inner skin, the metal layers were first formed with a patent pending rubber pad forming process. Between the formed metal layers, dry IM7 fabric and cyanate ester resin film is placed and by a film infusion process, the FML skin is produced.

The composite inner structure comprises of a fully integrated IM7 corrugated structure produced with vacuum infusion at elevated temperatures. The inner structure was produced in five sections. A modular mould system was designed to be able to produce all sections with a limited amount of moulds. The mould blocks were assembled on a simple flat aluminium plate. A binder powder was applied locally to the fibre reinforcement to allow for preforming of the complicated hingebeams and internal brackets. The infusion strategy was developed to minimise the cycle time and to reduce potential risk for air enclosures. A special resin degassing procedure was used to minimise the risk of outgassing during the infusion. After curing, the sections are cut to the correct dimensions. The corrugated core is then bonded in the inner skin, and additional fasteners are applied at the hinge bracket locations and at other highly loaded locations. Finally, the outer skin is bonded to the sub-assembly, post-cured and trimmed by water jet cutting. In a full-scale test on simulated acoustic fatigue, the computational results and the production process will be verified.

KEYWORDS

Vacuum infusion; High temperature Fibre metal laminates; Titanium; Cyanate ester resin;

1 INTRODUCTION

A project was started to demonstrate the potential of a high temperature fibre metal laminate in a primary structure aircraft component. A typical in-flight opening door of a fighter aircraft was selected as demonstrator part. Such a door is prone to foreign object damage and sonic fatigue for which an FML should have superb qualities. The design of the component has been established with a multi-disciplinary design team and common design procedures: create design concepts based on the requirements, analyze their mechanical behavior, check producibility aspects on small demonstrators, trade off the design concepts and choose the best for further evaluation. After the decision was made to actually build and test the component, the detailed engineering was carried out. This trajectory is described in more detail in reference 1. In this paper, the production aspects of the prototype will be described.

Figure 1: Exploded view of the internal composite structure of the door

2 PRODUCTION OF PARTS

2.1 SURFACE PRETREATMENT OF TITANIUM

To achieve good properties of the fibre metal laminate, the titanium sheets need to undergo a suitable surface pretreatment. Many surface pretreatments are known for titanium but most of these involve the use of harmful chemicals like HF solutions. Alternative surface pretreatments are aimed for which are less harmful and therefore easier and cheaper to implement in a production environment. Recently, solgel surface pretreatments have become commercially available. Coupon peel tests have shown that this solgel surface pretreatment yields similar bonding properties as the traditional HF surface pretreatment. Therefore, the following solgel procedure has been applied to the titanium sheets:

The titanium sheets are cleaned with Waterworks “Fresh start” using a Scotchbrite pad and distilled water. Then, the titanium sheets are sandblasted with 50-63 micron aluminium oxide grit using 30-80 psi oil-free nitrogen or clean, dry air pressure until a uniform matte appearance has been achieved. Then, the sheets are cleaned with “Fresh Start” again. The sheets are allowed to dry while the AC-130 solgel is mixed per kit procedure. The time between grit-blasting and sol-gel application shall not exceed 120 minutes. The solgel is applied by spray application onto the metal surface. If waterbreak occurs, the cleaning process is started again. The surface is kept continuously wet for 2 to 3 minutes without allowing the surface to dry during the entire application process. After the 2-3 minute wet time has elapsed, the surface is allowed to dry for a minimum of 60 minutes and a maximum of 120 minutes at ambient conditions. The sheets are arranged so that the solution will drain freely. BR 154 adhesive primer is applied within 120 minutes after the initial sol-gel application. The primer is dried for a minimum of 30 minutes and a maximum of 60 minutes prior to heat cure. The primer is cured for 60 ± 5 minutes at $250^\circ\text{F} \pm 5^\circ\text{F}$.

2.2 FIBRE METAL LAMINATE SKINS

The outer skin of the demonstrator is flat. From the experience with the GLARE material (reference 2 and 3), it is known that the autoclave prepregging process results in very good fibre metal laminates, as long as the laminates are flat, or just single curved. Recently, also slightly double curved sections of the A380 fuselage have been produced with the autoclave prepregging process. But for products with more three dimensional features, the prepregging process can result in voids near and in radii. Therefore, prepregging was chosen as production method for the flat outer skin only. For the inner skin, which is a double curved laminate, especially along the edges, a new production method needed to be developed. First, the metal sheets were formed in the desired shape. Since the formation of defect free thin products of these dimensions was not straightforward, a new patent pending metal forming process had to be developed. This process will be described in future papers. Then, after the surface treatment described in section 2.1, the FML was produced by a new, again patent pending film infusion process to overcome the problems with the traditional prepregging process. The materials used are IM7 fabric (Hexcel, Style 203, 4HS, IM7 6k), IM7 cyanate ester prepreg (Bryte, IM-7, 120gsm/EX-1551, 12) and cyanate ester resin film (Bryte, EX-1551 U, 0.016 psf, 12). Because of practical considerations, it was decided to produce the skins in two sections. For the double-curved innerskin, the lay-out of the rubber pad press did also impose limitations on the size of the sections. To create a continuous skin, the sections need to be joint together. This is done via a splice, see Figure 2.

Figure 2: Internal splice in FML skin

For Glare laminates, with aluminium sheets, the joggle in the metal at the start of the splice is created during the autoclave cycle. In titanium, it will not be possible to create this joggle just with autoclave pressure. Therefore, the joggle is created during the rubber pad forming process. The resulting inner and outer skin are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Outer skin (left) en inner skin

2.3 VACUUM INFUSION OF CORRUGATED CORE

The corrugation is a quasi-isotropic laminate from IM7-fabric. Both vacuum infusion and prepregging are suitable production methods. Since vacuum infusion offers a large potential for cost-savings, this process was used. Since vacuum infusion uses only one stiff mould system in combination with a flexible foil, this results in only one well defined surface. The other surface and laminate thickness will result from the used reinforcement and the process conditions.

Figure 4: The principle of the vacuum infusion process

Since the laboratory environment does not allow for the production of the corrugated core in one piece, the core is divided in 5 sections. Each section contains an hinge beam. To save costs, a modular, one-sided mould system is used. With a limited amount of aluminium beams, the moulds for all 5 sections can be assembled. The dimensions of the mould are corrected for thermal expansion. It is assumed that the carbon core will get its final geometry during the first 120°C cure. Compared to the thermal expansion of the aluminium mould,

the thermal expansion of the carbon core can be neglected. Therefore, the aluminium mould system is designed to have the correct dimensions also at 120°C.

Since part of this surface will have to be bonded to the skin, care must be taken that overlaps in the fabric are not located on the upper surfaces of the corrugations. A fabric with a preform binder is placed over the mould. Starting from one side, the fabric is draped over and into the mould. Where necessary, heat can be applied to keep the fabric in the deformed state. If the shape can not be laid up from one layer, cut must be made and a second layer can be placed, ensuring in minimal overlap of 20mm. The laminate is covered with a peel-ply and strips of resin flow material where needed. The whole lay-up is covered with nylon bagging film and sealed with a double seal. The airtightness is checked. The pressure is set to 20 mbars. The mould is heated. The resin is mixed, heated and degassed by an improved degassing procedure (reference 4). Then, the resin inlet is opened. After infusion, the injection pressure is increased to 300 mbars, after 5 minutes the resin inlet is closed.

Figure 5: Lay-up and infusion of corrugation element

The mould is heated to 120°C for 180 minutes. After this initial cure, the mould is heated to 150 and 180°C for the postcure cycle. After demoulding, the resin flow material and the peel-ply is removed and the corrugation section is trimmed to the correct dimensions. In Figure 6 two corrugation sections are shown.

Figure 6: Two corrugation sections with integrated hingebeam

2.4 PRODUCTION OF TITANIUM HINGES

During the (detail-) design phase of the weapon bay door, a selection for 5 hinges was made. The hinge brackets are attached to hingebeams which form an integral part of the corrugated inner structure. Due to a shallow recess in the inner skin, the construction is locally reduced in thickness. At the location of this dent, the hinge beam does not stretch over the full width of the door. The hinge bracket is also shorter at this location and not actuated. Although the hinge forces are different for all five hinge location, it was decided to design all remaining four brackets for the highest loaded location. This results in 2 different brackets designs. The brackets were from blocks of Titanium-AL6-V4. The brackets were milled at the Schiphol facilities of FAe with a 5-axis milling machine. The brackets are produced in two halves which will have to be welded in a subsequent step. A special welding jig was designed for clamping the two brackets-halves during welding. The welding is performed at the welding department at FAe using the TIG welding process. The welding is performed in two steps. In the first step, just a few spots are welded. In the second step, a continuous weld is applied. The areas where the brackets are to be bonded to the corrugation or the skin, the weld line is removed by sanding until a smooth surface is obtained. Pilot holes are drilled in the flanges of the brackets.

Figure 7: The brackets halves after milling, the bracket in the welding jig and the finished bracket

3 ASSEMBLY

With all the parts ready, the final assembly can commence. First the corrugation sections are trimmed to the correct length. Carbon coupling strips are bonded to the corrugation sections with a cyanate ester adhesive paste (Bryte EX-1537). The skin doublers are bonded to top and bottom of the corrugations. Then, the brackets are placed inside the cavities in the inner skin and the hinge beams. With the help of the pilot holes

in the brackets, holes are drilled through the brackets, skins and corrugation. The brackets are fixed temporarily with clamps. Then, a special drill tool is fixed on the brackets to be able to drill the holes in the hingebeam. This procedure is repeated for all 5 hinge brackets, see Figure 8.

Figure 8: Drilling of holes during the final assembly

With all holes drilled at 2.8mm, the holes in the hinge brackets are drilled to the correct size and blind nuts are placed, see Figure 9.

Figure 9: Drilling of holes in the titanium brackets and placement of blind nuts

With all holes drilled at the correct location, all parts are disassembled and cleaned. The corrugation sections are placed in the innerskin with bonding film and bonding paste at the correct locations and mechanical fasteners are placed. Various types of fasteners are used during the assembly, see Figure 10.

Figure 10: Various fastener types used during assembly

The assembled door is vacuum bagged and cured. The final door is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: The door after assembly (note: the contour still needs to be trimmed)

4 TESTING

The door has been designed for a full scale acoustic fatigue test. The test set-up and the results are described in reference 1. In Figure 12 the test set-up is shown.

Figure 12: The door in the acoustic fatigue test set-up at the NLR test facilities (photo copyright NLR)

The door did not fail in the test and has probably been designed too heavy due to conservative assumptions in the estimation of the allowables.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This project has shown the feasibility of a high temperature fibre metal laminate from IM7 fibres, titanium with a cyanate ester matrix and its application in a primary structural component with a double curved contour in a fighter aircraft. Probably, an alternative resin system will have to be selected, because of the brittle behaviour of the current system and the peel-sensitivity. For the demonstrator production, no optimisation steps were taken like the development of automated drilling and fastener placement, research into most suitable drilling tools and parameters. The project has also shown the potential of vacuum infusion as a low-cost production method for highly loaded primary aircraft structures. For space applications, similar projects have already been carried out (ref. 5).

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